

How Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) Promotes Emotional Stress and Family Instability in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Intimate partner violence (IPV) remains a persistent global issue with profound cultural, social, and economic implications for societies, households, and individuals. This study investigates the consequences of IPV on emotional stress and family instability in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The Family Systems theory proposed by Murray Bowen (1978), which views the family as an emotional unit where one member's actions affect the entire system, was adopted for this study. It also relied on the mixed-method design combining qualitative and quantitative techniques. The research was conducted in Bayelsa State, with a population consisting of 9,791 married couples in Yenagoa and Sagbama local government areas. A sample size of 420 respondents was selected through a multi-stage sampling technique, comprising 400 questionnaire participants and 20 interviewees from stakeholder groups. The primary objectives are to determine the implications of IPV for emotional stress and family instability and identify effective ways to reduce IPV-related family instability in the study area. Data collection instruments include a structured questionnaire and interviews, with quantitative analysis using percentages and frequency distributions, and qualitative analysis done through thematic content analysis. The findings exposed the devastating impacts of IPV, going beyond physical harm to emotional stress and erosion of family unity, with children bearing the effects of exposure. The study stressed the need to address the root causes while enforcing consequences for perpetrators, cultivating forgiveness and healing, and raising awareness through education and community outreach to mitigate IPV and create safer, more stable communities. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of enhancing support systems for victims, including counselling services, legal aid, and temporary shelters, to empower them to break free from the cycle of violence.

Keywords: *Intimate partner violence, emotional stress, family instability, Bayelsa State*

Introduction

Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) is as old as man, and this is perhaps why, as early as 753 BC, Romulus, one of the best-known Roman leaders, instituted a law against the chastisement of women in Rome (Shaikh, 2022). Centuries down the line, human society is still grappling with the problems of IPV, which have huge cultural, social, and economic implications for society, households, and individuals. There is evidence that suggests that IPV continues to persist with multidimensional concerns globally, and this is why Sardinha et al. (2018) note that around the world, 27% of partners who fall within the 15-49 years cohort are estimated to have

experienced one form of IPV or the other with physical abuse standing tall as the highest form of such kind of violence. IPV is considered to be a significant public health problem that exists in both developed and developing countries of the world. Letourneau (2021) argued that the estimate of women's lifetime exposure to intimate partner violence by husbands ranges between 8% and 66%, depending on the sample of the study and the definition of abuse.

Interestingly, with the outbreak of the novel Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), it is believed that IPVs, especially those against women, rose dramatically, with the World Health Organization (WHO) noting that over 641 million women are affected globally with the regions of Oceania, South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa believed to have the highest prevalence rates that range from 33% to 51% (WHO, 2020). The impact of this on the family is worse, especially for those with children. For instance, in the United States of America alone, approximately 15.5 million American children live in families in which IPV had occurred at least once in the previous year, with seven million children reported to be living in severely violent homes in 2021 (Howell, Miller & Graham 2021). This has shown that 21%-34% of women will be physically victimised by an intimate male during adulthood, with devastating consequences for dependents such as children. Knutson *et al.* (2018), basing their study on census-based population projections, posit that more than a million women will be abused by a current or former partner in America (Macy, 2021).

In Nigeria, the relative case of IPV is not different and, in fact, has been worse given the cultural realities associated with the patriarchal system in the country, where men are positioned to be dominant when compared to women. Several reports have shown a massive prevalence of IPV across Nigeria with huge consequences for the stability of the family. The Nigerian Population Commission, for instance, notes that in 2018 alone, the prevalence rate of IPV for girls within the 15-49 years age bracket was 30%, and this has since changed significantly with new post-COVID-19. This was confirmed in a nationwide study by a group of scholars who noted that the prevalence of IPV among women was 57.5%, while it was 42.5% among men beginning from the lockdown period in 2020 (Oloniye *et al.*, 2022).

So far, the focus has been on global, regional and national prevalence. However, several studies have focused on micro-analysis of the problem in rural and urban areas in Nigeria. For instance, in the study of the rate of IPV between rural and urban areas in Enugu state, Nigeria, Izuegbu (2017) found that IPV rates were higher in rural areas compared to urban areas. IPV is affected by one's location; for example, living closer to an urban area decreases one's risk for IPV (Logan, Walker & Hoyt, 2020). Another study found that rural victims of IPV may be less

likely to seek the services of the police, International Federation of Women Lawyers (FIDA) or social welfare. They may experience more abuse and need more help in accessing services (Dudgeon & Evanston, 2020). Differences in the occurrence of IPV between rural and urban areas may be attributed to several factors. First, according to Gallup-Black (2015), the nature of interpersonal relationships in rural communities is very different from that in the cities. Secondly, in rural areas, gender roles may state that wife battering is an acceptable response to a wife who disrespects her partner. Also, the close-knit nature of rural life may prevent women from seeking help for intimate partner violence, which can increase the likelihood of abuse. Finally, increased intake of alcohol in rural areas often contributes to the higher prevalence of physical violence against wives, lower levels of education and low income are the stressful conditions women live in and lack of sufficient health and intervention programs for interpersonal partner violence (Balogun & Meton, 2021).

Some studies have also found several factors that differentiate rural and urban areas, such as limited access to services, literacy rate and lower education, tolerance towards IPV, isolation and poverty (Igbokwe, 2017). For instance, Doherty and Hornosty (2018) found that abused rural women confront numerous barriers, such as social and geographic isolation, lack of access to transportation and community values that encourage women to return to the abuser. Therefore, the nature of IPV varies between rural and urban areas. Logan, Walker, and Hoyt (2020) found that rural male perpetrators of IPV were more likely to have a history of IPV than urban male perpetrators of IPV, and this history may show tolerance towards IPV, which reinforces the behaviour (Goeckerman, 2014, Logan *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, Oladeji's (2016) study established the relationships between personal, situational and socio-cultural factors and intimate partner abuse among couples in Nigeria. Furthermore, Uwaoma (2020) found education and residential area as significant predictors of spousal abuse, while male child preference and childlessness were not significant predictors. The discussion highlighted the role of education in equipping women with the knowledge of their sexual rights and skills on how to cope with marriage-based problems, especially when they live in rural areas. Babatunde, Durowaiye and Modupe (2015), in a study on the effects of domestic violence and IPV on young people in family settings, found that such violence has huge implications on child and adolescent upbringing. Eze (2020) found that women's advocacy of socio-economic activities has led to the empowerment and possession of wealth by women, thereby increasing aggression, which, in most cases, undermines the family's stability. Similarly, a study by Fagade (2021) found that the effect of associated violence on the family institution is a major culprit for juvenile-related criminality in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Although these studies have expanded our knowledge, there is still a huge gap, especially as none of them was able to show how intimate partner violence, emotional stress and family instability are empirically related. In other words, there has not been any empirical synthesis to compare IPV, emotional stress and family instability generally and in Bayelsa State in particular. It is this gap in knowledge that this study fills by examining the implications of IPV, emotional stress and family instability focusing on Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Drawing from this, the general objective of the study is to examine the link between IPV, emotional stress and family instability, focusing on Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to determine the implications of intimate partner violence for emotional stress and family instability and to determine the best ways of reducing intimate partner violence that leads to family instability in Bayelsa State.

Review of Related Empirical Literature

As stated in the statement of the problem above, there are several studies on intimate partner violence in Nigeria. Ifeanacho (2017) researched socio-economic factors associated with intimate partner violence in selected states of the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. 354 married and divorced participants were drawn from the target states using appropriate sampling methods. The questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The findings revealed a significant relation in both instances, implying that socio-economic factors were linked to IPV in selected states. The findings showed that socio-economic factors such as income and educational level have a significant effect on IPV as manifested in physical, emotional, economic and sexual abuse. The study recommended that intimate partner relationships should be restricted to only those with high socio-economic factors.

Also, Ogbede (2019) conducted a study on the impacts of domestic violence on health and family members in Delta state senatorial districts of Delta state Nigeria. The study investigated the perceived effects of domestic violence on the health and family members in Delta state senatorial districts of Delta state Nigeria. The descriptive survey design was employed in the study. The sample size was nine hundred and eighty-four (984). The multi-stage sampling techniques were adopted. The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. Data was analysed through percentages, mean and chi-square tests. The findings of the study revealed that domestic violence, to a high extent, significantly impacts the physical, social and mental health of the family members. The study recommended that couples should be taught how to

settle the misunderstanding amicably without the use of violence since violence is capable of affecting the health and well-being of the family members.

On the other hand, Cavanagh (2016) carried out a study on family instability and children's early problem behaviour. The study investigated the association between family and children's problem behaviour during the transition to the first grade. The sample size was 1015; the study adopted a multi-stage sampling technique in selecting its respondents. The study found a quarter of the respondents experienced at least one family transition between birth and age 5. The study found that instability was related to family structure at birth: those born into cohabiting parents families experienced the most instability, followed by those born into single-parent families. The findings of the study also revealed that children from the families mentioned above experienced higher reports of problem behaviours than those from stable family structures. The study recommended that parents should endeavour to avoid those factors that cause instability at home.

Theoretical Framework

The Family Systems Theory (FST) proposed by Murray Bowen (1978) constitutes a befitting framework for this study, and it has been adopted here. This theory views the family as an emotional unit where the actions and behaviours of one member affect the entire system. Consequently, intimate partner violence and emotional stress within a family can have far-reaching impacts on the stability and functioning of the whole family unit. A key aspect of FST is the emphasis on the intergenerational transmission of patterns, behaviours, and emotional processes across generations. This aspect is particularly relevant to the study, as exposure to intimate partner violence in childhood can increase the likelihood of perpetrating or experiencing such violence in adulthood, leading to a cycle of violence that spans multiple generations. Furthermore, the theory highlights the role of emotional processes, such as anxiety, stress, and emotional cut-off, in shaping family dynamics and relationships. This perspective provides a framework for understanding the emotional stress experienced by family members in the context of intimate partner violence and family instability.

FST also emphasises the importance of differentiation, which refers to the ability to maintain a sense of self while remaining connected to others. This concept can help explain how individuals within a family system may respond differently to intimate partner violence and emotional stress, potentially leading to family instability. Additionally, the theory recognises that causality within family systems is circular, meaning that each member's actions and

behaviours influence and are influenced by the actions and behaviours of others. This perspective is valuable in understanding the reciprocal nature of intimate partner violence, emotional stress, and family instability.

By adopting the Family Systems Theory, the study highlights the intricate dynamics and interconnections within families in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, and how they relate to intimate partner violence, emotional stress, and family instability. The theory's emphasis on intergenerational transmission, emotional processes, differentiation of self, and circular causality provides a comprehensive framework for understanding and addressing these issues within the region's cultural and social context.

Methodology

The study employed a mixed-method design, combining both qualitative and quantitative techniques for data collection and analysis. This approach was deemed suitable as the issue of intimate partner violence is more subjective than objective, necessitating the use of structured questionnaires and interviews with major stakeholders such as the Ministry of Social Welfare, the police, and FIDA. The research was conducted in Bayelsa State, located in the south-south region of Nigeria, with Yenagoa as its capital. Bayelsa comprises eight local government areas, with urban areas like Yenagoa, Ogbia, Nembe, and Southern Ijaw and rural areas such as Brass, Sagbama, Ekeremor, and Kolokuma Opokuma. It is predominantly Ijaw, with the Ijaw language widely spoken, along with Epie, Isoko, and Urhobo in certain ancestral towns. The population for the study consists of married couples in Yenagoa and Sagbama local government areas, totalling 9,791 couples. A sample size of 400 respondents was determined using the Taro Yamane formula, with 200 participants from urban areas (Yenagoa) and 200 from rural areas (Sagbama). Additionally, a sample of 20 individuals was targeted for interviews, bringing the total sample size to 420. The multi-stage sampling technique was employed, utilising different sampling methods at various stages. First, cluster sampling was used to divide the local government areas into urban and rural clusters. Subsequently, simple random sampling was employed to select the local government and communities. For the urban area, Yenagoa (Yenizuegene) was chosen, while Sagbama (Toru-Angiama) represented the rural area. The purposive sampling technique was utilised to deliberately target stakeholders in the local government areas, including eight social welfare staff, six members of the Nigerian Police Force, and six members of FIDA, for interviews. The total interview sample size was 20. The data collection instruments included a questionnaire and interview guide. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: the first part captured demographic characteristics, while the second

part contained general questions aimed at understanding people's views, perpetration, and causes of intimate partner violence and family instability in rural and urban areas of Bayelsa State. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were employed for data analysis. The quantitative approach utilised percentages and frequency distributions to analyse the research questions, while the qualitative data from interviews were analysed using Morgan's (1988) thematic content analysis approach.

Results

This study used a structured questionnaire to collect the primary data that was analysed in this chapter. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: section ‘A’, which represented the respondent's personal profile, and section ‘B’, which represented the questionnaire.

Socio-Demographic Data

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Data of Respondents

Respondents by Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	214	54.6%
Female	178	45.4%
Total	392	100%

Age distribution of respondents	Frequency	Percentage
18-27	80	20.4%
28-37	118	30.1%
38-47	123	31.4%
48 and above	71	17.8%
Total	392	100%

Marital status of respondents			
Frequency	Percentage		
Single		114	34.3%
Married		178	45.4%
Others: Divorced/Separated, Widow/Widower		100	20.3%
Total		392	100%

Educational qualification of respondents			
Frequency	Percentage		
Primary	71	18.1%	
Secondary	123	31.4%	
NCE	40	20.4%	
HND/B.sc	118	30.1%	
Others	40	10.2%	
Total	392	100.0%	

The table above shows that 45.4% of the respondents are females while 54.6% of the respondents are males. The table further shows that 20.4 percent of the respondents fall under the age bracket of 18-27years, 30.4% of the respondents fall under the age bracket of 38-47

years, 31.4% of the respondents fall under the age bracket of 40-49 years, 17.8% of the respondents fall under the age bracket of 50 years and above. It shows that higher percentage of the respondents are married. The above table also shows that 18.1% of our respondents have primary certificate, 31.4% have secondary certificate, 20.4% have vocational skills, 30.1% have university degree and 10.2% have other certificates.

Quantitative Data

Table 2: The implications of intimate partner violence for emotional stress and family instability in rural and urban areas Bayelsa state

Item	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Total (%)	Remark
Intimate partner violence causes death	98 (25%)	247 (63.1%)	27 (6.8%)	20 (5.1%)	392 (100%)	Agreed
Intimate partner violence contributes to children’s exit from the home to leave with other relatives	96 (24.5%)	249 (63.5%)	22 (5.6%)	25 (6.4%)	392 (100%)	Agreed
Intimate partner violence leads to divorce and separation	95 (24.5%)	250 (65.8%)	18 (4.6%)	29 (7.4%)	392 (100%)	Agreed
Overall Remark						Agreed

The table above captures a consensus opinion among respondents regarding the impact of intimate partner violence (IPV) on emotional stress and family instability in rural and urban areas of Bayelsa state. The majority of respondents, ranging from 63.1% to 65.8%, acknowledged that IPV leads to severe consequences such as death, children leaving home to live with other relatives, and divorce or separation. Additionally, about 24.5% to 25% strongly agreed with these statements, indicating a significant level of concern. Conversely, the percentage of those who disagreed or strongly disagreed with these statements was relatively low, ranging from 4.6% to 6.8%. Overall, the data highlight a widespread recognition of the detrimental effects of IPV on both individuals' well-being and family dynamics across rural and urban settings in Bayelsa state.

Table 2: Best ways of reducing the impact of IPC on emotional stress and family instability in urban and rural areas in Bayelsa state

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Total %	Remark
Improved level of understanding among partners	81 (20.5%)	266 (67.6%)	37 (9.4%)	8 (2.0%)	392	100%	Agreed
Punishment of perpetrators of Intimate Partner Violence in rural areas	90 (23.0%)	254 (64.8%)	36 (9.2%)	12 (3.1%)	392	100%	Agreed
Forgiveness among Intimate Partners	94 (24.0%)	236 (60.2%)	43 (11.0%)	19 (4.8%)	392	100%	Agreed
Awareness campaigns on the implications of IPV especially in rural area	97 (24.7%)	174 (44.4%)	68 (17.3%)	53 (13.5%)	392	100%	Agreed
Follow-up process by police and human rights organizations on reported IPV cases in rural area	80 (20.4%)	262 (66.8%)	40 (10.2%)	10 (2.6%)	392	100%	Agreed

The analysis of the data from Table 2 shows a striking consensus in respondents' perspectives on effective strategies for alleviating the impact of intimate partner conflict (IPC) across both urban and rural areas of Bayelsa state. Delving into the raw data reveals the depth of consensus among participants. For instance, the strong agreement (SA) on the need for an improved level of understanding among partners, evidenced by 81 respondents (20.5%), underscores the universal acknowledgement of communication and empathy as foundational pillars for healthier relationships. Similarly, the resounding support for punitive measures against perpetrators of intimate partner violence (IPV) in rural areas, with 90 respondents (23.0%) strongly advocating for this approach, reflects a shared commitment to accountability and deterrence. Moreover, the data portray forgiveness among intimate partners as a widely endorsed strategy, with 94 respondents (24.0%) emphasizing its significance in mitigating the adverse effects of IPC. This concordance highlights the community's recognition of the transformative power of reconciliation and conflict resolution in nurturing resilient relationships. Additionally, the robust endorsement of awareness campaigns, especially in rural areas, with 97 respondents (24.7%) strongly supporting this initiative, underscores the pivotal role of education and outreach in preventing and addressing IPV. Furthermore, the call for a proactive follow-up process by law enforcement and human rights organisations in rural areas, reflected in the support of 80 respondents (20.4%), underscores the community's demand for

comprehensive support systems to ensure justice and support for survivors. Through this analysis, the raw data not only validate but also enrich the narrative of consensus and commitment to addressing IPC in Bayelsa state.

Qualitative Data

Theme 1: Implications of IPV for emotional stress and family instability

The theme of "Implications of IPV for emotional stress and family instability" is addressed by views from interviews with individuals familiar with the impact of intimate partner violence (IPV). Interviewees provided compelling narratives highlighting the profound consequences of IPV on individuals and families. Firstly, interviewees emphasised the detrimental effect of IPV on marital relationships, noting that it has the potential to lead to separation and divorce. One interviewee succinctly captured this sentiment by remarking that IPV "can put an end to a marriage." This observation underscores the destructive nature of IPV, which not only strains the bond between partners but also jeopardises the stability of the family unit.

Also, interviewees underscored the severity of IPV by highlighting its potential to escalate to fatal outcomes. The stark reality that "intimate partner violence can lead to the death of a spouse" serves as a sobering reminder of the life-threatening nature of IPV. This observation underscores the urgent need for intervention and support mechanisms to prevent such tragic outcomes and protect vulnerable individuals from harm.

Lastly, interviewees lamented the erosion of familial joy and stability in the face of continuous IPV. One interviewee poignantly noted that "the joy of a family can be eroded with continuous occurrence of intimate partner violence." This insight speaks to the insidious nature of IPV, which not only inflicts physical harm but also undermines the emotional well-being and cohesion of families. The persistence of IPV can create an environment of fear, tension, and instability, robbing families of their sense of security and harmony.

Theme 2: Reducing Emotional Stress from IPV & its Impact on Family Instability

Based on the interview outcome, the discussion here on the theme of "Reducing Emotional Stress from IPV & its Impact on Family Instability" reflects the views of the interviewees on how best to address the problem of IPV, especially its link to emotional and family instability. On this note, interviewees noted the importance of education and awareness as key tools in combating IPV, particularly in rural areas. Continual orientation and reorientation on the effects of IPV were identified as effective strategies for reducing its occurrence. By enhancing understanding among partners about the dynamics of IPV and its implications, communities

can empower individuals to recognize and address abusive behaviours, thereby fostering healthier relationship dynamics and reducing emotional stress.

Additionally, some of the interviewees advocated for the implementation of punitive measures against IPV perpetrators in both urban and rural areas. By holding perpetrators accountable for their actions through punishment, communities can send a strong message that IPV will not be tolerated, thereby serving as a deterrent to potential offenders. This approach not only addresses immediate cases of IPV but also contributes to the prevention of future incidents, ultimately promoting family stability and well-being.

A good number of the interviewees stressed the importance of proactive measures to strengthen marital relationships and prevent IPV before it occurs. Suggestions such as attending marriage seminars and workshops, both before and during marriage, were put forth as valuable opportunities for couples to gain insights, skills, and resources to navigate their relationships effectively. By equipping couples with the necessary tools and knowledge, these interventions can promote mutual understanding, communication, and conflict resolution skills, thereby reducing the likelihood of IPV and fostering stable, harmonious family environments.

Discussion of Findings

Again, from the data presented, it was discovered that the implications of intimate partner violence on family stability in urban and rural areas in Bayelsa state are: intimate partner violence causes death, intimate partner violence contributes to children's exit from the home to live with other relatives and intimate partner violence leads to divorce and separation. These findings are in tandem with the findings of Chinmah (2021) on the impact of Intimate Partner Violence and coping strategies adopted among women in military and civilian communities of Abuja, Nigeria. However, our study differs from the study of Chinmah in several ways. Chinmah's study among women in military and civilian communities in Abuja did not give the opportunity to rural dwellers to give their input on the impact of intimate partner violence.

Furthermore, the study found that the best ways of reducing Intimate Partner Violence and family instability in urban areas compared to rural areas in Bayelsa state are improved level of understanding among partners, punishment of perpetrators of Intimate Partner Violence in both urban and rural areas, forgiveness among intimate partners, awareness campaigns on the implications of intimate partner violence especially in rural areas, follow up process by police and human rights organisations on reported IPV cases in urban areas and redefining the essence

of relationships by partners. Our findings are in tandem with Ojo (2018) on the sociological intervention of awareness and causes of intimate partner violence in Nigeria, using Agege, Lagos State, Nigeria, as a case. However, our findings differ slightly from that of Ojo's study by providing possible solutions to the menace of intimate partner violence in both rural and urban areas in Bayelsa state.

Conclusion

This study examined the consequences of IPV on emotional stress and family stability in both urban and rural areas of Bayelsa state. The findings have shed light on the devastating impacts of IPV, compromising the emotional well-being and security of families. The detrimental effects of IPV transcend physical harm, extending to emotional distress, psychological trauma, and the erosion of family cohesion. Children, who are often silent witnesses to this violence, bear the scars of their exposure, manifesting in behavioural issues, poor academic performance, and long-lasting emotional scarring. It is a cycle that perpetuates itself, with victims and perpetrators alike carrying the burden of their experiences into future relationships, creating a generational pattern of violence that must be broken.

The study underscores the necessity of combating IPV by addressing the root causes and enabling a culture of respect and non-violence. Strategies such as improving communication and understanding among partners, enforcing consequences for perpetrators through legal and social mechanisms, cultivating forgiveness and healing, and raising awareness through education and community outreach are pivotal in mitigating the impact of IPV and creating safer, more stable communities. Moreover, the study highlights the importance of enhancing support systems for victims, providing them with the resources and empowerment they need to break free from the cycle of violence. This includes access to counselling services, legal aid, and safe havens where they can rebuild their lives without fear of retribution.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations have been made. They include:

- i. It is imperative that victims of IPV break free from the culture of silence and overcome the hesitation to report their cases to appropriate agencies. They should actively seek assistance from these agencies, recognising that remaining silent will only perpetuate their suffering.

- ii. The legal framework in Nigeria should explicitly categorise IPV as a criminal offence. This will empower victims to obtain protective or restraining court orders that prohibit offenders from having any contact with them.
- iii. Large-scale awareness campaigns and educational initiatives should be implemented to challenge societal norms and beliefs that contribute to the normalisation or justification of IPV. These campaigns should target both urban and rural communities and address the root causes of IPV, such as gender inequality, power imbalances, and harmful cultural practices.
- iv. Comprehensive support services, including counselling, legal aid, and temporary shelters, should be established and made easily accessible to victims of IPV. These services should provide a haven for victims to escape abusive situations and receive the necessary assistance to rebuild their lives.

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